

Using Machine Learning to Improve Settlement Classification Methods for Urban Landscape

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Summary

To expand on existing methodology and improve settlement classification, a machine learning and geostatistical approach is explored to classify urban landscapes into residential, non-residential and mixed uses. The mixed use class is defined as buildings with a combination of residential and non-residential uses. This will further improve our understanding of urban systems and also support a more accurate estimation of population mapping within urban areas.

KEYWORDS: Settlement classification, Urban analytics, building footprints, machine learning

Introduction

Urban settlements are growing in size, dimension, and complexity (Jochem et al., 2021). Characteristics such as multistorey buildings, and mixed-use buildings are becoming the norm across many urban systems. In current approaches to settlement (buildings) classification, using satellite mapping or satellite-derived analysis, residential and non-residential use have been established and defined as relevant classes (Schiavina et al., 2022). However, in urban areas, there is an increasing number of multistorey buildings due to the vertical growth of development. In urban landscapes, both single-storey and multistorey buildings have tendencies to have within them a combination of multiple uses, termed mixed-use e.g. residential and non-residential (Evans, 2014; Vorontsova et al., 2016). This blurs the line between the binary classification of residential and non-residential used by existing methodologies for settlement (buildings) classification. Therefore, it is important to expand the settlement classification of urban landscapes into three classes – residential, non-residential and mixed (a combination of residential and non-residential). This will enhance our understanding of urban settlements and is also linked to an improved understanding of population distribution across space in urban settlements.

Methodology

A satellite-derived building footprint dataset was used in combination with georeferenced administrative building datasets from Lagos, Nigeria with building use information to train a building classification model. A machine learning model and a geostatistical model approach are explored. Using the building use information, the proportion of residential, non-residential and mixed-use buildings per 1 x 1 kilometre grid cell was calculated for observed locations. 47 predictive covariates are produced at the same spatial resolution. These covariates were chosen based on previous population and settlement modelling research efforts. For the geostatistical approach, a hierarchical Bayesian model was implemented with the proportion of each settlement class as the outcome variable. This is run in an Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA) model combined with Stochastic Partial

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Differential Equation (SPDE). The machine learning model selected is a Random Forest ensemble model which was used as a regression model to produce the same outcome variable, proportions of residential, non-residential and mixed-use buildings per 1 x 1 kilometre grid cell respectively. The output predictions will be compared with Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) and other available settlement classification datasets available to assess how comparable they are.

Expected results

The result of the models produced a predicted output of the proportion of residential, non-residential and mixed-use buildings per grid cell at a 1 x 1 kilometre spatial resolution, as shown in Figure 1. The Random Forest model result achieved an out-of-sample Pearson correlation of 0.72 and 0.66 for non-residential and residential respectively. Also, the hierarchical Bayesian model result achieved an out-of-sample Pearson correlation of 0.71 and 0.84 for non-residential and residential respectively. The mixed class output is derived from the modelled result of the residential and non-residential and was still being processed at the time of this submission. The result of the model was intentionally calculated as the proportion of building per 1 x 1 kilometre for each building use class. With this output, depending on the use case, the count or area of building footprints per 1 x 1 kilometre grid cell can be derived for each building use class. One important benefit of the Bayesian models is the ability to calculate the uncertainty estimates associated with each prediction and this better helps with the understanding of the limitation of the predictions. The Random Forest and Bayesian models will also be compared to understand if there is any skewness in the accuracy of the prediction based on the model type and parametrization. Accuracy statistics such as correlation coefficient, mean error, mean absolute error and root mean square error will be calculated to compare predictions with Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) and available settlement classification datasets.

Figure 1: Random Forest predicted proportion (range 0 – 100%) of residential buildings per 1 x 1 kilometre grid cell across Lagos, Nigeria

Outlook for the future

The understanding of urban settlements are more important today as urban areas around the world continue to outgrow rural communities. Settlement analytics and methodologies that integrate not only the horizontal spread but also the vertical growth become a timely and important research area (Farjam & Motlaq, 2019). This research can also support small area demographic mapping, particularly in urban areas where demand for finer geographical details to support official statistics and other urban analytical insights are increasing (Jochem et al., 2021; Schweers et al., 2016). This could inform new ways of looking at land use management, resource distribution and urban growth models. The identification of residential, non-residential and mixed-use is a novel approach that supports the exploration of other complexities within urban settlements. In addition, the settlement classification output in this research could be used as an input dataset in current population estimation methodologies to improve its accuracy. In the methodology presented, mixed-use is still grouped, and could be a combination of

residential or non-residential. But future analysis could expand to looking at estimating the percentage combination of residential and non-residential that makes up mixed-use and if there is a threshold variation across space.

Biographies

Wole Ademola Adewole is a PhD researcher at the University of Southampton with research interest in population mapping and distribution, population movement, urban analytics, GIS.

Ortis Yankey is a research fellow at Worldpop, a research group at the University of Southampton. His research interests are population modelling, spatial epidemiology and health/medical geography

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Samantha Cockings is an associate professor at the School of Geography and Environmental Science, University of Southampton where she explores her interest in automated zone design, spatiotemporal population modelling and environment and health.

Andrew J Tatem is a professor at the University of Southampton and also the director at WorldPop, a research group at the University of Southampton. His research interest includes developing approaches to map population distribution, and understanding drivers of small area demographic heterogeneities,

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